

Plasma Proteins: An Overview

Chauhan JM^{1*}, Rathod PG², Baraiya PD³, Dubariya UJ⁴

^{1*}Department of Veterinary Pathology, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Kamdhenu University, Junagadh, Gujarat, India

²Department of Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Kamdhenu University, Navsari, Gujarat, India

³Department of Veterinary Pathology, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Kamdhenu University, Navsari, Gujarat, India

⁴Department of Veterinary Surgery and Radiology, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Kamdhenu University, Navsari, Gujarat, India

Introduction

Blood-proteins, also termed plasma proteins, are proteins present in blood plasma. They serve many different functions, including transport of lipids, hormones, vitamins and minerals in activity and functioning of the immune system. Other blood proteins act as enzymes, complement components, protease inhibitors or kinin precursors. Contrary to popular belief, haemoglobin is not a blood protein, as it is carried within red blood cells, rather than in the blood serum. Serum albumin accounts for 55% of blood proteins and is a major contributor to maintaining the oncotic pressure of plasma and assists, as a carrier, in the transport of lipids and steroid hormones. Globulins make up 38% of blood proteins and transport ions, hormones, and lipids assisting in immune function. Fibrinogen comprises 7% of blood proteins; conversion of fibrinogen to insoluble fibrin is essential for blood clotting. The remainder of the plasma proteins (1%) are regulatory proteins, such as enzymes, proenzymes, and hormones. All blood proteins are synthesized in liver except for the gamma globulins.

There are several plasma proteins of which examples of specific blood proteins are;

- Prealbumin (transthyretin)
- Alpha 1 antitrypsin
- Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein
- Alpha-1-fetoprotein

- Alpha 2-macroglobulin
- Gamma globulins
- Beta-2 microglobulin
- Haptoglobin
- Ceruloplasmin
- Complement component 3 (Protein of Immune system)
- Complement component 4 (Human Leukocyte Antigen)
- C-reactive protein (CRP)
- Lipoproteins
- Transferrin
- Prothrombin
- MBL or MBP

Prealbumin (transthyretin)

Transthyretin (TTR or TBPA) is a transport protein in the plasma and cerebrospinal fluid that transports the thyroid hormone thyroxine (T₄) and retinol to the liver. This is how transthyretin gained its name: *transports thyroxine and retinol*. The liver secretes TTR into the blood, and the choroid plexus secretes TTR into the cerebrospinal fluid. TTR was originally called prealbumin (or thyroxine-binding prealbumin) because it migrated faster than albumin on electrophoresis gels. Prealbumin was felt to be a misleading name, it is not a synthetic precursor of albumin (Rayazi *et al.*, 2003).

Alpha 1 antitrypsin

Alpha-1-antitrypsin or α_1 -antitrypsin (A1AT, α_1 AT, A1A-or AAT).is protein belonging to the serpin superfamily. It is encoded in humans by the *SERPINA1* gene. A protease inhibitor, it is also known as alpha₁-proteinase inhibitor (A1PI) or alpha₁-antiproteinase (A1AP) because it inhibits various proteases (not just trypsin). In older biomedical literature it was sometimes called serum trypsin inhibitor (STI, dated terminology), because its capability as a trypsin inhibitor was a salient feature of its early study (Richler *et al.*, 2017).

Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein

Orosomucoid (ORM) or alpha-1-acid glycoprotein (α_1 AGP, AGP or AAG) is an acute phase

protein found in plasma. It is an alpha-globulin glycoprotein and is modulated by two polymorphic genes. It is synthesized primarily in hepatocytes and has a normal plasma concentration between 0.6–1.2 mg/mL (1–3% plasma protein). Plasma levels are affected by pregnancy, burns, certain drugs, and certain diseases, particularly HIV. The only established function of ORM is to act as a carrier of basic and neutrally charged lipophilic compounds (Penny *et al.*, 2014).

Alpha2-macroglobulin

α_2 -Macroglobulin (α_2 M), or alpha-2-macroglobulin, is a large (720 KDa) plasma protein found in the blood. It is mainly produced by the liver, and also locally synthesized by macrophages, fibroblasts, and adrenocortical cells. In humans, it acts as an inhibitor of fibrinolysis by inhibiting plasmin and kallikrein. It functions as an inhibitor of coagulation by inhibiting thrombin.

Alpha-1-fetoprotein

Alpha-fetoprotein (AFP, α -fetoprotein; also sometimes called alpha-1-fetoprotein, alpha-fetoglobulin, or alpha fetal protein) is a protein that in humans is encoded by the *AFP* gene. The *AFP* gene is located on the *q* arm of chromosome 4 (4q25). Maternal AFP serum level is used to screen for Down syndrome, neural tube defects, and other chromosomal abnormalities. AFP is a major plasma protein produced by the yolk sac and the fetal liver during fetal development. It is thought to be the fetal analog of serum albumin. AFP binds to copper, nickel, fatty acids and bilirubin and is found in monomeric, dimeric and trimeric forms (Mizejewski, 2003).

Gamma globulins

Gamma globulins are a class of globulins, identified by their position after serum protein electrophoresis. The most significant gamma globulins are immunoglobulins (antibodies), although some immunoglobulins are not gamma globulins, and some gamma globulins are not immunoglobulins.

Beta-2 microglobulin

β_2 microglobulin also known as B2M is a component of MHC class I molecules, MHC class I molecules have α_1 , α_2 , and α_3 proteins which are present on all nucleated cells (excludes red blood cells). In humans, the β_2 microglobulin protein is encoded by the *B2M* gene (Güssow *et al.*, 1987).

Haptoglobin

Haptoglobin (abbreviated as Hp) is the protein that in humans is encoded by the *HP* gene. In blood plasma, haptoglobin binds with high affinity to free hemoglobin released

from erythrocytes, and thereby inhibits its deleterious oxidative activity. Compared to Hp, hemopexin binds to free heme. The haptoglobin-hemoglobin complex will then be removed by the reticuloendothelial system (mostly the spleen). In clinical settings, the haptoglobin assay is used to screen for and monitor intravascular hemolytic anemia. In intravascular hemolysis, free hemoglobin will be released into circulation and hence haptoglobin will bind the hemoglobin. This causes a decline in haptoglobin levels (Schaer et al., 2014).

Complement component 3 (Protein of Immune system)

Complement component 3, often simply called C3, is a protein of the immune system. It plays a central role in the complement system and contributes to innate immunity. In humans it is encoded on chromosome 19 by a gene called *C3*.

Complement component 4 (Human Leukocyte Antigen)

Complement component 4 (C4), in humans, is a protein involved in the intricate complement system, originating from the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) system. It serves a number of critical functions in immunity, tolerance, and autoimmunity with the other numerous components. Furthermore, it is a crucial factor in connecting the recognition pathways of the overall system instigated by antibody-antigen (Ab-Ag) complexes to the other effector proteins of the innate immune response (Sekar *et al.*, 2016).

C-reactive protein (CRP)

C-reactive protein (CRP) is an annular (ring-shaped) pentameric protein found in blood plasma, whose circulating concentrations rise in response to inflammation. It is an acute-phase protein of hepatic origin that increases following interleukin-6 secretion by macrophages and T cells. Its physiological role is to bind to lysophosphatidylcholine expressed on the surface of dead or dying cells (and some types of bacteria) in order to activate the complement system via C1q. CRP is synthesized by the liver in response to factors released by macrophages and fat cells (adipocytes). It is a member of the pentraxin family of proteins (Pepys and Hirschfield, 2003).

Lipoproteins (chylomicrons, VLDL, LDL, HDL)

A lipoprotein is a biochemical assembly whose primary function is to transport hydrophobic lipid (also known as fat) molecules in water, as in blood plasma or other extracellular fluids. They consist of a triglyceride and cholesterol center, surrounded by

a phospholipid outer shell, with the hydrophilic portions oriented outward toward the surrounding water and lipophilic portions oriented inward toward the lipid center. A special kind of protein, called apolipoprotein, is embedded in the outer shell, both stabilising the complex and giving it a functional identity that determines its role.

Transferrin

Transferrins are glycoproteins found in vertebrates which bind to and consequently mediate the transport of iron (Fe) through blood plasma. They are produced in the liver and contain binding sites for two Fe^{3+} ions. Human transferrin is encoded by the *TF* gene and produced as a 76 kDa glycoprotein. Transferrin glycoproteins bind iron tightly, but reversibly. Although iron bound to transferrin is less than 0.1% (4 mg) of total body iron, it forms the most vital iron pool with the highest rate of turnover (25 mg/24 h). Some invertebrates have proteins that act like transferrin found in the hemolymph. When not bound to iron, transferrin is known as "Apotransferrin" (Kawabata, 2019).

Prothrombin

Thrombin (EC 3.4.21.5, *fibrinogenase, thrombase, thrombofort, topical, thrombin-C, tropostasin, activated blood-coagulation factor II, blood-coagulation factor IIa, factor IIa, E thrombin, beta-thrombin, gamma-thrombin*) is a serine protease, an enzyme that, in humans, is encoded by the *F2* gene. Prothrombin (coagulation factor II) is proteolytically cleaved to form thrombin in the clotting process. Thrombin in turn acts as a serine protease that converts soluble fibrinogen into insoluble strands of fibrin, as well as catalyzing many other coagulation-related reactions (Royle *et al.*, 1987).

MBL or MBP

Mannose-binding lectin (MBL), also called mannan-binding lectin or mannan-binding protein (MBP), is a lectin that is instrumental in innate immunity as an opsonin and via the lectin pathway.

Ceruloplasmin

Ceruloplasmin (or caeruloplasmin) is a ferroxidase enzyme that in humans is encoded by the *CP* gene. Ceruloplasmin is the major copper-carrying protein in the blood, and in addition plays a role in iron metabolism. It was first described in 1948. Another protein, hephaestin, is noted for its homology to ceruloplasmin, and also participates in iron and probably copper metabolism. It is copper

carrying protein in the blood, Synthesized in liver. Caeruloplasmin functions as ferroxidase and superoxidase scavenger. Clinical significance of Ceruloplasmin is;

- Elevated level of Caeruloplasmin in:
- Oestrogen-related effect
- Pregnancy
- Low level of Caeruloplasmin in:
- Wilson disease
- Nephrotic syndrome (Worthley *et al.*, 2005).

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